

Latin America Woody Vegetation Structure and Change (LAM WVSC), 2015-2023

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1. Introduction and Objectives

A comprehensive woody vegetation structure and change data are essential for modeling biomass, estimating greenhouse gas emissions, reporting changes in forests and trees outside forests, and planning and monitoring forest restoration and conservation activities. Existing medium-resolution (10-30 meters per pixel) spatial datasets are insufficient for these applications. Land cover classification maps such as PRODES (Messias et al., 2024), MapBiomass (Souza et al., 2020), and WorldCover (Zanaga et al., 2021) lack vegetation structure data such as tree canopy cover and height. Annual forest loss data (Hansen et al., 2013) do not show changes in tree canopy structure. Forest structure maps (Potapov et al., 2022) provide sufficient structure data for the analysis within tall dense tree stands. However, these maps are less useful for savanna and dry woodland areas. None of the existing products provide annual continental woody vegetation structure and change data needed to harmonize national reporting and regional studies.

We aimed to fill this gap by providing comprehensive annual woody vegetation structure and dynamics data for Latin America from 2015 to 2023 at a medium (30 meters per pixel) spatial resolution. To generate these products, we used state-of-the-art methods and tools such as Landsat Analysis Ready Data (Landsat ARD), the ARD-based annual land surface phenology and change detection features, locally calibrated regression tree ensemble models for annual woody vegetation structure mapping, annual forest loss and degradation detection tools, and temporal filters that improve interannual map consistency (Potapov et al., 2019; 2020; 2021; 2022; Turubanova et al., 2023).

The annual dataset is available online for free, with no restrictions on access, redistribution, or use, as long as proper citation is given, following the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY). For the user's convenience, the data is provided in two formats: raster image tiles and public Google Earth Engine assets. Detailed information about the data format and access is provided in Section 4. The annual dataset can be viewed online using the Google Earth Engine Apps interface: <https://glad-other.projects.earthengine.app/view/latinamericawvsc20152023>.

This document briefly outlines the methodology and serves as a user guide for the Latin America annual Woody Vegetation Structure and Change (LAM WVSC) dataset. A detailed description of the methods and product validation report are being prepared.

2. Source Data

2.1. Landsat Analysis Ready Data

The Landsat satellite program, operated jointly by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) provides optical observation data records suitable for annual vegetation structure assessment at medium spatial resolution (Wulder et al., 2012). Recent advances in Landsat archive data processing enabled off-the-shelf time series products that can be efficiently used as input for continental-scale mapping. For this project, we used the Landsat Analysis Ready Data developed by the Global Land Analysis and Discovery Lab at the University of Maryland (Landsat ARD; Potapov et al., 2020). The ARD dataset consists of 16-day global Landsat image composites made from the best-quality observations, available since 1997, and operationally updated. Each composite contains a normalized surface reflectance of six reflective bands (blue, green, red, NIR,

SWIR1, and SWIR2), land surface brightness temperature, and an observation quality flag. The quality flag is based on the CFMask cloud and shadow detection system from Landsat Collection 2 and global quality assessment models (Potapov et al., 2020). It helps select clear-sky observations, identifies water and snow/ice, and flags observations affected by topographic shadows or cloud proximity.

The Landsat ARD product is stored in geographic coordinates (WGS84) and has a spatial resolution of 0.00025 degrees per pixel (about 30 m per pixel at the Equator). The data is distributed free of charge without restrictions on subsequent redistribution or use. The product can be accessed via a public API at <https://glad.umd.edu/ard>.

2.2. Woody Vegetation Cover Reference Data

We define woody vegetation canopy cover (WVCC) as a proportion of the Landsat 30-m pixel covered by the vertical crown projection of trees and shrubs that are 2 meters tall or higher; the crown projection includes within-crown gaps. Pixels with a canopy cover below 10% are not included in our product.

WVCC cannot be directly measured using medium-resolution imagery such as Landsat, thus we used higher spatial resolution calibration data for empirical modeling of this variable. The most practical way to obtain WVCC reference data is by using high spatial resolution (1-3 m per pixel) canopy height models (CHM) derived from airborne lidar (ALS) observations (Potapov et al., 2019). However, there is no ALS coverage over Latin America sufficient for continental model calibration. An alternative approach is using very high-resolution optical data for canopy cover mapping. This method, however, cannot directly estimate canopy height, which makes it difficult to apply the exact definition of woody vegetation.

For our analysis, we used the woody vegetation canopy cover product developed by the World Resources Institute (WRI) using 2020 Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data at the spatial resolution of 10 m per pixel (Brandt et al., 2023). The WRI map was calibrated using tree presence data manually collected from very high resolution (≤ 1 m per pixel) WorldView imagery. Tree presence was defined by the overlap of the 10×10 m pixel centroid with the visually interpreted tree crown projection. The map shows the probability that the pixel centroid intersects with the tree canopy. Brandt et al. (2023) demonstrated that the tree extent probability value (percent) is consistent with the reference tree canopy cover. The original WRI map only covers tropical forests. To allow for continental model calibration, the WRI team applied the existing canopy cover model to regularly spaced image chips that cover 10% of the Latin American land area outside tropical forests.

The WRI map considers “woody vegetation that is either >5 m in height regardless of canopy diameter or is between 3 and 5 m in height with a crown of at least a 5-m diameter” (Brandt et al., 2023). We compared the WRI tree canopy cover data with the available ALS data in Latin America. The comparison showed that the WRI product is consistent with a lidar-based canopy cover of vegetation that is at least 2 meters tall. We use the 2 m height threshold as our woody vegetation definition. This definition is consistent with the WRI product over Latin America, and it ensures that short woody vegetation types such as Caatinga xeric shrublands are included.

The WRI map excludes “tall herbaceous vegetation such as sugarcane, bananas, and cacti, and short woody crops such as tea and coffee”, while “agroforestry, rotational and non-rotational tree plantations and trees in urban areas” were included (*ibid*). Our product follows the same properties; banana and coffee plantations are excluded, while agroforestry (including orchards) and rural and urban trees are included.

We calculated the average tree extent probability at 30-m pixel resolution for the Landsat-based product calibration, hereafter referred to as canopy cover. A 1% random data subset was set aside for model uncertainty evaluation. These set-aside pixels were not used for model calibration.

The 10 meters per pixel WorldCover 2021 land cover product (Zanaga et al., 2021) was used as a reference dataset for mapping WVCC. The WorldCover includes three categories of woody vegetation:

tree cover, shrubland, and mangroves. We resampled these three classes to the 30-m spatial resolution, calculating the percent cover of the 10-m resolution class area per Landsat pixel. This combined tree and shrub cover map for 2021 was used as reference data to detect commission errors, i.e., pixels where WorldCover does not detect woody vegetation presence while our intermediate map result and/or WRI tree canopy cover map shows canopy cover of 10% and higher. However, the WorldCover product was not directly used for WVCC model calibration.

2.3. Woody Vegetation Height Reference Data

To calibrate our Landsat-based model, we used vegetation height data collected by two NASA spaceborne lidar instruments: the Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) sensor onboard the International Space Station and the Advanced Topographic Laser Altimeter System (ATLAS) onboard the ICESat-2 satellite.

GEDI is a full waveform lidar designed specifically to measure vegetation structure, operated from 2019 to 2023 (Dubayah et al., 2020). GEDI data is limited to the area north of 51.6° S latitude and does not cover Southern Patagonia. The data represent waveform return metrics for each 25 m diameter laser footprint. A set of relative height of returned energy (RH) metrics that reflect the vegetation height is provided by the data archive (Dubayah et al., 2021). We used the RH98 metric (98th percentile of returned energy) which represents the top of the tree canopy within the GEDI footprint. To select only the highest quality growing season GEDI observations, we applied a set of filters following the method described in Potapov et al. (2021) and excluded winter-time leaf-off data in Patagonia. For each selected observation, we rasterized the GEDI RH98 metric value in integer decimeters for a Landsat 30-m pixel that includes the center of the observation footprint.

ATLAS is a photon-counting laser instrument designed for precise elevation data collection (Neuenschwander and Pitts, 2019). It provides a global sample of elevation data from 2018 to the present. Vegetation structure metrics are derived from photon height values for fixed 100-meter and 20-meter orbital track segments. The only metric available for the 20-meter segments is the 98% relative canopy height, which is similar to the GEDI RH98. We applied filters to include only the best-quality growing season data for model calibration. The center of each 20-m segment was used to select a single Landsat 30-m pixel to rasterize the height value in decimeters.

The data from both GEDI and ATLAS instruments were combined into a single reference dataset. Similar to the canopy cover data, we used 99% of the data for model calibration and set aside a 1% random subset for model uncertainty evaluation.

Our definition of the vegetation canopy height (WVCH) is based on the calibration data and corresponds to the RH98 GEDI metric and the ATLAS 98% relative canopy height. We compared these lidar-based height metrics with the tree height distribution statistics derived from high spatial resolution ALS-based CHM within a Landsat pixel. This comparison showed that the spaceborne lidar metrics reflect the 93rd percentile of ALS-based tree canopy height within the pixel. Thus, our WVCH map represents the 93rd percentile of ALS-based woody vegetation canopy height within a Landsat pixel with at least 10% canopy cover.

3. Methodology

3.1 ARD-based Features and Auxiliary Data Inputs

To simplify vegetation structure mapping, we aggregated the Landsat ARD 16-day clear-sky time series into annual rank-based statistics used as inputs for classification and regression models (Potapov et al., 2020; 2022; Turubanova et al., 2023). Two independent sets of features were calculated for each year: (1) annual land surface phenology features for vegetation structure modeling, and (2) annual change detection features for detecting woody vegetation cover loss and degradation. A detailed explanation of the

phenology and change detection features is presented by Potapov et al. (2020). We used a freeware system (GLAD Tools, available from <https://glad.umd.edu/ard>) to process Landsat ARD data.

To create annual land surface phenology features we used clear-sky observations from the 16-day Landsat ARD composites from the corresponding year. We extracted three sets of data distribution statistics: (1) annual distribution of normalized surface reflectance and vegetation indices values including minimum and maximum values, quartiles, interquartile averages, and amplitudes; (2) seasonality statistics, calculated from the observation time series ranked by vegetation index and brightness temperature values (e.g., the reflectance band value corresponding to the annual maximum surface temperature); and (3) vegetation phenology statistics (start, peak, and end of the growing season) based on the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) time series. We implemented gap-filling to complete the time series for years with more than a two-month gap without cloud-free observations. We used data from up to four preceding years to fill these gaps.

The annual change detection features were designed to detect woody vegetation disturbance. These features highlight abrupt changes in spectral reflectance between observations made during the same season in the current and preceding years. To generate each annual feature set, we used clear-sky Landsat ARD observations from the current and three preceding years. For the three preceding years, we used the mean reflectance value for each 16-day interval. Three types of features were extracted from the Landsat ARD time series. First, we calculated distribution statistics for the current and preceding years, similar to the phenology features, and computed the difference for each statistic between these years. Second, we computed the difference in spectral reflectance between the current and preceding years for each 16-day interval and extracted distribution statistics from the time series of difference values to highlight changes in seasonal reflectance. Third, we calculated the slope of the linear regression between spectral value and observation dates.

We used the land surface elevation data combined from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (Reuter et al., 2007) and Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (Danielson and Gesch, 2011) as additional inputs for woody vegetation canopy structure modeling and change detection.

3.2. Woody Vegetation Canopy Cover Mapping

For empirical modeling of the annual WVCC, we implemented a set of locally calibrated regression tree model ensembles (Potapov et al., 2021; 2022; Turubanova et al., 2023). A separate model was calibrated for each Landsat ARD 1×1 degree tile. Each model represented an ensemble of 25 bagged (bootstrap aggregated) regression trees (Breiman et al., 1984) calibrated using the software based on the R ‘rpart’ package (<https://cran.r-project.org/package=rpart>). The median value of the 25 models was used as the model output.

The calibration data (dependent variable) consisted of the 2020 WRI woody vegetation canopy cover calculated from the original 10-m spatial resolution product (Brandt et al., 2023; see Section 2.2). For pixels that did not experience forest loss (see Section 3.3) and were outside woody vegetation extent mask derived from the WorldCover product (see Section 2.2) the canopy cover was set to zero. The independent variables included phenology features for the year 2020 and land surface elevation. For each tile and each tree model in the ensemble, we extracted 5,000 random samples (Landsat pixels) for model calibration.

To ensure the spatial consistency of the locally calibrated models, the training data for each tile were collected from the target and neighboring tiles. Within tropical forests, where complete coverage of the WRI canopy cover data was available, we used tiles within a 1-degree radius around the target tile. The window was expanded by 1 degree if the number of selected tiles was less than 9 (e.g., in coastal areas). For the rest of Latin America, where only 10% of the land area was covered with WRI calibration data, we used tiles within a 2-degree radius and expanded it until at least 12 tiles were found. For the Galapagos Islands, we calibrated a single model for the entire archipelago.

To generate a temporally consistent model, we added training data through the iterative active learning process. The initial model, calibrated using year 2020 data only, was applied to all years, 2015 to 2023. Through visual product analysis, we selected areas where the model outputs were unstable while no changes in WVCC were observed. For these areas, we extracted training data for all years (2015-2023) for pixels where no tree canopy cover change was mapped by the existing forest change products (Hansen et al., 2013; Potapov et al., 2022). Another set of training data was selected using pixels where WVCC overestimation was detected through a comparison with the WorldCover woody vegetation extent map. For these pixels, we assigned zero canopy cover value. We appended the original training data set with these additional training samples and re-calibrated the models for the affected tiles. Several iterations were performed to create the final continental product.

3.3. Woody Vegetation Cover Disturbance Detection

We define the woody vegetation cover disturbance as an abrupt event that causes a reduction of canopy cover within the Landsat pixel. We mapped two types of disturbance: (1) canopy loss, defined as an event of complete or nearly complete removal of live woody vegetation canopy at the Landsat pixel scale; and (2) canopy degradation defined as an event of partial live canopy removal at the Landsat pixel scale.

Woody vegetation canopy loss includes areas where trees or tall shrubs were mechanically removed, burned, broken and uprooted by wind, permanently flooded, or most of the tree canopy in the top layer was dead due to disease or insect infestation. Two approaches were used to map canopy loss: direct detection (this Section), and detection based on WVCC time series analysis (Section 3.5, see Step 5 of the filter algorithm). Based on visual analysis of intermediate products, we suggest that within dense, tall forests most canopy loss events were detected directly, while some disturbances within short, sparse woodlands were omitted by the direct mapping model and detected through the WVCC time series analysis.

To calibrate the direct canopy loss detection model, we partitioned Latin America into 14 regions with different forest change dynamics using Hansen et al. (2013) annual forest loss data as a reference. For each region, we calibrated a separate annual change detection model using manually collected samples of the presence and absence of woody vegetation canopy loss. Each model represented an ensemble of 25 decision trees calibrated using all training data collected within the region. The training data were collected for the entire interval, 2015-2023. The year of forest disturbance was automatically assigned to each training pixel using the anomalies detected within the SWIR1 and NDVI annual time series. The model predictors (independent variables) included Landsat change detection features and land surface elevation (Section 3.1). The training data collection was done iteratively. The new training data were added if, after the model application, we visually observed map errors. The model calibration approach was identical to the forest disturbance detection method developed by Potapov et al. (2019) and Turubanova et al. (2023). The WVCC mask was not used during the canopy loss mapping.

Woody vegetation canopy degradation includes the following change scenarios: (1) mixed pixels with partial canopy removal on the edges of canopy loss patches; (2) areas with scattered tree/shrub damage caused by wind, fire, or water; (3) scattered tree removal within selective logging areas; and (4) areas of intensive shifting cultivation, pasture, and agroforestry management characterized by a small-scale mosaic of temporary clearings within secondary forests, shrubs, or tree plantations. We mapped canopy degradation only within WVCC extent ($WVCC \geq 10\%$) and outside loss areas. We implemented the same modeling principles and regions as for the canopy loss mapping. Training data were manually collected within the 2023 WVCC extent, and the model was applied only within the respective WVCC extent of each year.

3.4. Woody Vegetation Canopy Height Mapping

Our approach for woody vegetation canopy height (WVCH) mapping is similar to the approach used by Potapov et al. (2021) and Turubanova et al. (2023). The WVCH was estimated using a set of locally

calibrated empirical models, where a separate ensemble of 25 regression trees was calibrated for each Landsat ARD 1×1 degree tile. The calibration data included the aggregated GEDI RH98 metric and ATLAS 98% canopy height, rasterized to Landsat pixels. We extracted model calibration data for each year, 2018-2023, using the (a) corresponding lidar observation as the dependent variable and (b) Landsat phenology features from the same year and land surface elevation as the independent variables. The WVCC product was used to filter the lidar observation data; for samples with <10% WVCC the lidar height was set to zero. For each year and regression tree model, we extracted 1% of the training data per 1×1 degree tile.

To calibrate each regression tree model for each tile, we aggregated training data from the target and neighboring tiles for all years (2018-2023). The neighboring tiles were defined with a radius of 3 degrees. The radius was expanded for up to 7 degrees until the total number of training samples (Landsat pixels) reached at least 350,000. The WVCH model was calibrated and applied to each tile only once, without iterations.

3.5. Temporal Filtering and Woody Vegetation Change Analysis

Despite applying rigorous Landsat data preprocessing and calibration data filtering, the annual WVCC and WVCH model outputs had interannual fluctuation, particularly in dry seasonal woodlands and areas with low clear-sky observation frequency. Thus, the goals of temporal filtering were: (1) to remove errors and interannual fluctuation in model outputs; (2) to integrate WVCC and WVCH measurements and change detections; (3) to detect WVCC loss events missed by the disturbance detection model; and (4) to identify WVCC and WVCH gain events.

The following steps describe the per-pixel temporal filter algorithms, criteria, and the sequence of operations:

1. We filled in WVCC/WVCH data for years with no Landsat observations using data from neighboring years and/or pixels.
2. We set WVCC/WVCH values to zero for all years for a pixel that (i) has no detected disturbance events, (ii) has the year 2023 $WVCC \leq 10\%$, and (iii) satisfies one of the following conditions: (a) has less than 3 years with $WVCC > 10\%$, or (b) located within 1-pixel distance from stable water bodies.
3. To avoid double counting of the same disturbance event, we removed the annual loss and degradation detection if it occurred within 3 years (5 years for degradation events) after a disturbance detected earlier.
4. The WVCC and WVCH time series were filtered to remove single-year anomalies. This step was applied only to pixels where direct disturbance mapping models did not detect canopy loss or degradation.
5. The algorithm detected additional WVCC loss events if the cover decreased from $\geq 25\%$ to zero and stayed below 10% for at least 2 years after the reduction.
6. Additional degradation events were added within a 1-pixel buffer of loss pixels of the same year if WVCC decreased abruptly by at least 10%.
7. We used a set of criteria to detect WVCC/WVCH increases between years. Specifically, we selected pixels with a consistent WVCC increase of $\geq 10\%$ between the current and preceding years (i.e., the maximum WVCC value before the current year was smaller than the minimal value after the current year by at least 10%). Pixels with WVCH increase were selected by comparing the maximum and minimum values between the first and the last three years of the time series. For pixels with detected disturbance, the rules for WVCC/WVCH gain detection were applied separately before and after the disturbance event.
8. All pixels with no detected disturbance or increase of WVCC or WVCH between 2015 and 2023 were considered stable, and the median value for the 2000-2023 interval was used for each year of the time series.

9. For pixels with disturbance detection after 2015, the median values of structure measurements were assigned for years before the event (unless gain was detected before the loss event).
10. For pixels where a disturbance event was detected, we set the output canopy structure values based on the disturbance date, duration, and intensity. For loss detection, the cover and height values are set to zero for the disturbance year. For degradation, we set the WVCC and WVCH to the minimum value of the disturbance year and the following two years. If no change in WVCC is detected during the year of the degradation event, we set the value to 10% lower than the value in the previous year. After the disturbance event, we keep the structure measurements constant until an increase is detected (see Step 7).
11. The WVCC and WVCH values during the WVCC/WVCH gain years were calculated using linear regression, which estimated the value for the current year based on model outputs from up to three preceding and following years. The range of years used for the regression model was limited by change events.
12. We applied the following filters to ensure consistency in the final time series: (i) for years with $WVCC < 10\%$, both cover and height values were set to zero; (ii) for years with $WVCC \geq 10\%$, the minimum WVCH was set to 2 m; (iii) the annual increase in TCC and TCH was limited to 50% and 5 m, respectively.

Based on the final filtered WVCC and WVCH time series, we created the annual Woody Vegetation Structure Change (WVSC) product that highlights the interannual dynamics of structure variables. Each pixel within an annual WVSC layer has one of the following codes:

0. No detected change.
1. WVCC/WVCH removal, which is represented by a reduction of cover and height values to zero.
2. WVCC degradation, which is represented by WVCC reduction and (not always) WVCH reduction.
3. WVCC/WVCH establishment, which is represented by the increase of cover and height from zero to $\geq 10\%$ and ≥ 2 m, respectively.
4. WVCC and/or WVCH enhancement, which is represented by the increase of cover and/or height values.

These layers, subsequently, were used to determine the first year of loss, disturbance (loss + degradation), or gain for the dynamics overview output layers.

Continental woody vegetation structure and change mapping workflow

4. Product Access and Metadata

The Latin America Woody Vegetation Structure and Change (LAM WVSC) dataset is available online with no charges for access and no restrictions on subsequent redistribution or use, as long as the proper citation is provided as specified by the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY).

The data are provided as raster GIS layers in two formats: GeoTIFF files and Google Earth Engine (GEE) assets. The GeoTIFF dataset is distributed as 10×10 geographic degree tiles. The tiles share the same data format:

Coordinate System: EPSG 4326 (WGS 1984)

Projection: Geographic coordinates

Pixel Size: 0.00025 × 0.00025 degrees

Data Format: 16-bit unsigned (WVCH) or 8-bit unsigned (all other layers), LZW-compressed.

10×10 degrees tiles map

4.1. Annual Woody Vegetation Canopy Cover (WVCC)

Woody Vegetation Canopy Cover (WVCC) is a proportion of the Landsat 30-m pixel covered by the vertical crown projection of trees and shrubs that are 2 meters tall or higher; the crown projection includes within-crown gaps. WVCC raster data represent the integer percent canopy cover with the range 10-100%. The data format is 8 bits unsigned.

WVCC GEE assets

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2015
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2016
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2017
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2018
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2019
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2020
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2021
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2022
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCC_2023

WVCC raster tiles

https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2015/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2016/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2017/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2018/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2019/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2020/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2021/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2022/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCC_2023/

4.2. Annual Woody Vegetation Canopy Height (WVCH)

Woody Vegetation Canopy Height (WVCH) is the height of the top of the woody vegetation canopy within the pixel. WVCH corresponds to GEDI RH98 metric, ATLAS 98% canopy height, and the 93rd percentile of canopy height derived from the high spatial resolution ALS-based CMS model. WVCH raster data represent the integer canopy height value in decimeters with the range 20-450 dm. The data format is 16 bits unsigned.

WVCH GEE assets

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2015
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2016
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2017
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2018
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2019
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2020
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2021
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2022
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVCH_2023

WVCH raster tiles

https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2015/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2016/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2017/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2018/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2019/

https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2020/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2021/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2022/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVCH_2023/

4.3. Annual Woody Vegetation Structure Change

The Woody Vegetation Structure Change (WVSC) data highlights the annual dynamics of structure variables. Each pixel within an annual WVSC layer has one of the following codes:

0. No detected change.
1. WVCC/WVCH removal, which is represented by a reduction of cover and height values to zero.
2. WVCC degradation, which is represented by WVCC reduction and (not always) WVCH reduction.
3. WVCC/WVCH establishment, which is represented by the increase of cover and height from zero to $\geq 10\%$ and ≥ 2 m, respectively.
4. WVCC and/or WVCH enhancement, which is represented by the increase of cover and/or height values.

The data format is 8 bits unsigned.

WVSC GEE assets

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2015
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2016
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2017
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2018
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2019
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2020
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2021
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2022
https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/WVSC_2023

WVSC raster tiles

https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2015/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2016/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2017/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2018/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2019/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2020/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2021/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2022/
https://glad.umd.edu/users/Potapov/WVSC_Latin_America/Tiles_10d/WVSC_2023/

4.4. Dynamics Overview Layers

The following layers are provided as Google Earth Engine assets only. They represent the earliest year of the detected woody vegetation cover disturbance event. Unlike annual change layers (WVSC), these layers do not provide information about repeated disturbances. The pixel value is the year of the earlier change detection in format [year – 2000] (e.g., value 15 represents the year 2015). The data format is 8 bits unsigned.

The first year of WVCC removal

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/Loss_year

The first year of WVCC degradation

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/Degradation_year

The first year of WVCC disturbance (degradation or removal)

https://code.earthengine.google.com/?asset=projects/glad/LAM_WVSC/Disturbance_year

4.5. Product Visualization in Google Earth Engine

The WVCC, WVCH, and change layers can be viewed online using the Google Earth Engine Apps interface: <https://glad-other.projects.earthengine.app/view/latinamericawvsc20152023>. The interface provides the capability to display annual and multi-year data and analyze woody vegetation structure changes.

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